

Diaspora Remittances and Economic Growth in Nigeria: An ARDL Approach

Eyo Itam Eyo¹, John Ugah¹, Stella Ogwih-Ebelle¹

¹Department of Banking and Finance

University of Calabar

Calabar – Nigeria

Correspondence: eyoakamba@unical.edu.ng, eyoakamba@gmail.com

DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17088490>

Abstract

This paper examines the impact of diaspora remittances on Nigeria's economic growth, utilising total remittances and exchange rates as proxies for independent variables, with gross domestic product (GDP) as the dependent variable. The Autoregressive Distributed Lag (ARDL) method was applied to analyse secondary time series data from the Central Bank of Nigeria (CBN) and the World Bank Development database, covering the period from 1987 to 2021. The results show that, in the long term, remittances from the diaspora have a negative impact on Nigeria's economic growth, although this effect is not statistically significant. Conversely, an unstable exchange rate significantly hinders economic growth. While the benefits of remittances and exchange rate stability to economic development are limited, both factors are beneficial in the short term. Additionally, the impact of remittances varies, exhibiting either positive or negative effects depending on the lag used. Furthermore, the study highlights both short-term and long-term effects of exchange rate volatility on Nigeria's economic growth. The findings suggest that the Nigerian government should increase investment in infrastructure and improve access to amenities to attract more investors and boost investment levels. It also recommends further research to explore the post-COVID-19 effects of diaspora remittances on Nigeria's economic growth, considering currency fluctuations.

Keywords: Diaspora, Remittances, Economic growth, Trade Openness, UNCTAD

Introduction

Diaspora remittances are essential in supporting both government and household finances, offering vital income, savings, and consumption resources. When properly managed, these funds can foster development and help meet specific economic targets (Zainab, 2021). In Nigeria, remittances from citizens abroad, together with foreign direct investment (FDI), are expected to play a significant role in advancing the nation's economic goals and promoting overall growth (Asogwa & Osondu, 2014). Therefore, the financial contributions of migrant workers are critical for strengthening the development of monetary and financial markets in emerging economies.

Research by Giuliano and Ruiz-Arranz (2006) highlights that remittances allow low-income individuals to bypass credit limits, improve the use of capital, offset limited financial resources, and drive economic growth. Through their remittances and investments, migrants make significant progress towards sustainable development, especially in fighting poverty, eradicating hunger, promoting good health, providing quality education, ensuring access to clean water and sanitation, creating decent jobs, fostering economic growth, and reducing inequalities.

However, several obstacles hinder the smooth flow of remittances to Nigeria. High exchange rates, steep transfer fees, limited options for receiving funds, rising interest rates, and the government's difficulty in keeping inflation within single digits all substantially impact the transfer of these resources. Moreover, Nigeria's economy faces numerous structural, fiscal, monetary, and social challenges that have diminished investor confidence. Factors such as political instability, corruption, increasing inflation, poor governance, limited trade openness, and widespread insecurity—aggravated by crises

during and after elections—have made it difficult to attract and sustain the necessary levels of FDI (Adenike, 2021).

When families become overly dependent on remittances from relatives abroad, it can discourage their involvement in the labour market, making it difficult to secure livelihoods and increase national productivity. As a result, this reliance may reduce the labour supply, negatively impacting overall economic output. Evidence indicates that individuals who receive remittances tend to show lower levels of labour market participation and workforce engagement.

Several studies, including Adewale, Ameji, & Solomon (2021), Mgbarine, Olulu, & Lawrence (2022), Orekoya & Tijan (2023), and Ibrahim, Bajoon & Ezra (2024), have examined the relationship between diaspora remittances and economic growth, using various variables and reaching different conclusions. As a result, this research adds to the expanding literature on the subject and aims to determine whether remittances from diaspora residents contribute to Nigeria's economic growth, with particular attention to the impact of the COVID-19 pandemic. The specific objectives of the study are to:

1. Assess the contributions made by Nigerians now residing in other countries to the growth of the economy of their nation.
2. Analyse how the currency exchange rate has impacted the development of the Nigerian economy.

The research would benefit both international and domestic investors by guiding them on which economic sectors are suitable for investment. This, in turn, could lead to the creation of new jobs and more opportunities as investors start new businesses globally. It could also help increase family income and boost individuals' purchasing power, both of which would support the growth of the targeted economies. The business community will find the research very useful, as it will provide them with sufficient knowledge about the country's economic policies, enabling them to make more informed financial decisions.

Review of Related Literature

Conceptual Review

Since the early 1960s, diaspora remittance has played a vital role in Nigeria's economic growth, as expatriates aimed to improve their families' financial wellbeing back home. The significance of remittances grew markedly in the late 1980s when the value of the naira began to fluctuate against the dollar, encouraging many Nigerians abroad to send money home for greater purchasing power. The emergence of international money transfer organisations (IMTOs), such as Western Union and MoneyGram, simplified these transactions, allowing expatriates to support their families (Adolphus, 2021).

According to the Central Bank of Nigeria (CBN), remittances from Nigerians abroad fell markedly from \$23.4 billion in 2019 to about \$16.9 billion in 2020, serving as a vital financial lifeline for the country. Remittances made up roughly 6.1% of Nigeria's GDP in 2018, making Nigeria the second-largest recipient in Africa, behind Egypt. The World Bank projected further declines in remittances, citing alternatives like blockchain-based platforms (Adolphus, 2021). President Muhammadu Buhari highlighted that annual remittances of around \$25 billion accounted for more than 80% of the government's budget, emphasising their importance in alleviating poverty and strengthening the economy (Akin, 2020). Additionally, in 2017, remittances reached \$22 billion, far exceeding the country's net foreign aid that year.

Despite the important role of remittances, Nigeria faces challenges, including high transfer costs, which limit its potential for increased remittances compared to other African countries. For example, Egypt received \$29.6 billion in remittances in 2020, thanks to lower transfer costs and more efficient systems. The economic impact of COVID-19 further worsened the decline in remittances to Nigeria, dropping by 27.7% from 2019 to 2020 (Zainab, 2021).

To increase remittance inflows during this economic downturn, Nigeria can learn from the experiences of other countries. The Nigerians in Diaspora Commission (NIDCOM) could enhance its efforts to better utilise diaspora funds for poverty reduction and economic growth. Possible strategies include launching pilot programmes across different geopolitical zones and establishing the Diaspora Investment Development Division (DIDD) to promote investment by Nigerians abroad. The DIDD could also consider issuing a Diaspora Bond to fund specific development projects, adopting a more structured approach to the capital market.

Exchange Rate and Economic Growth in Nigeria

The exchange rate indicates how one currency can be exchanged for another and plays a vital role in influencing the private sector's participation in international trade, as well as in determining the prices of domestic and imported goods (Samuel, 2021). It has a significant impact on key economic factors, including local prices, trade income, wealth distribution, and investment decisions. Therefore, regulators strive to keep a stable exchange rate to achieve goals such as full employment, fair income distribution, and economic growth.

Stable exchange rates have bolstered the economies of advanced countries, while many African nations, including Nigeria, face challenges due to frequent fluctuations in exchange rates (Godwin & Sergius, 2021). Recently, pressures on Nigeria's external reserves have caused the naira to steadily depreciate against major currencies. In November 2022, the official exchange rate was about 442 naira per USD, while the parallel market rate soared to around 750 naira, indicating significant instability in the foreign exchange system.

As Nigeria marked 62 years of independence, the naira's value continues to decline, with a 63% gap between the official and parallel markets—the highest in 17 years. This indicates a 22.4% devaluation of the naira since late December 2021, as the premium in the parallel market rose from 33.3% at the end of 2021 to 63% in 2022, exceeding the IMF's recommended rate of 5%. The primary reason for the naira's decline is Nigeria's reliance on crude oil for foreign currency. The economic repercussions of COVID-19, including falling oil prices and rising costs of fuel imports and subsidies, have exacerbated dollar shortages, further weakening the naira.

Empirical review

Many studies have examined how diaspora remittances relate to economic growth. Gelb et al. (2021) noted that data on diaspora investments remains limited, despite improvements in remittance collection. Meanwhile, Ugherughe and Okonkwo (2020) found a long-term, one-way link from remittances to Nigeria's GDP from 1977 to 2017, suggesting that legal migration might boost technology transfer and economic progress.

Lynne (2013) studied the impact of Kenyan remittances on economic growth using multiple regression analysis. The results showed that remittances significantly influence Kenya's economy, prompting the government to bolster the institutions that support them. David (2015) emphasised the potential of diaspora contributions in achieving the UN's 2030 Agenda for Sustainable Development, calling for collaboration among diaspora members, policymakers, and scholars.

Suman et al. (2021) examined the causal relationship between remittances and economic development in BRICS countries. Their analysis revealed a positive effect of remittances on bank deposits. Andualem (2021) documented the negative effects of COVID-19 on African remittances and suggested comprehensive government relief measures to mitigate these impacts. Oluyemi et al. (2015) investigated the effect of Nigerian expatriates' remittances from Ghana, finding substantial positive impacts on Nigeria's economic development. Ariam and Lucas (2018) concluded from their literature review that remittances positively influence economic development, urging policymakers to establish favourable conditions for remittance inflows.

Onah (2010) studied how remittances affect poverty and human capital development in Nigeria. He found that remittances help reduce poverty and improve education, but they negatively impact health outcomes. Meanwhile, Adenike (2021) identified a strong link between migrant remittances and Nigeria's GDP, suggesting that policymakers should improve remittance channels and investment prospects.

Kalandi and Charan (2016) used panel VECM data to demonstrate a long-term equilibrium between remittances and economic growth in BRICS countries, showing a negative long-term impact on GDP per capita. Onyeisi and Anoke (2018) identified a negative correlation between overseas development aid and domestic lending in Nigeria, supporting the promotion of remittances through official channels. Ozigbu (2018) employed a Bounds Test Strategy to assess the socioeconomic effects of remittances, concluding that they significantly contribute to reducing poverty in Nigeria. Jiang et al. (2019) analysed the roles of remittances, foreign direct investment (FDI), and exports in overall development in West Africa, emphasising the positive influence of these factors on development while also highlighting the complex relationship between FDI and economic growth.

Finally, Muriel (2015) studied the impact of remittances on West African countries. She discovered that while remittances had a negative effect on the GDP of Cameroon and Cape Verde, they had a positive influence on Senegal and Nigeria, demonstrating that productive investments from remittances are essential for economic growth.

Theoretical framework

This study employs two key theories, namely exogenous growth theory and the altruism theory.

Exogenous Growth Theory

Robert Solow (1956) introduced the exogenous growth theory as a vital part of the neoclassical model of economic development. According to this theory, economic growth primarily stems from technological progress that is independent of economic conditions. It proposes that external factors, rather than internal ones, are responsible for most growth. The core idea is that economic success mainly depends on external, autonomous forces rather than on interconnected internal elements.

This theory is relevant to the research because it indicates that in an economy with free trade, rapid technological development and overall GDP growth can occur. According to the exogenous growth theory, diaspora remittances are considered an external factor that can significantly impact economic growth if utilised effectively. Therefore, the theory holds importance for the study due to this key relationship.

Altruism Theory

Auguste Comte introduced the concept of altruism in the 1850s and has been studied by various scholars to explain the primary motivations behind remittances (Becker, 1981; Stark, 1995). The altruistic perspective suggests that immigrants often send money mainly to improve the well-being of their extended family members. However, this view does not dismiss the fact that immigrants also tend to prioritise their own needs and often make personal sacrifices to support their families. It is widely recognised that the desire to help family members significantly influences the amount of money sent home (Stark, 1985).

Migrants' affection and sense of duty towards their families, communities, and countries motivate their remittance behaviours. According to the theory of giving as a source of happiness, immigrants find fulfilment in sending money home, as it helps improve social welfare in their places of origin (Becker, 1981).

If altruism is regarded as the sole motive for remitting, it is expected that remittances will increase over time (Stark, 1995). Conversely, a decline in remittances could negatively impact economic output in the recipient country, while an increase is likely to stimulate economic activity in the destination

country. Furthermore, the economic benefits experienced by recipients in their home country are strongly linked to the volume of remittances sent from the host country.

The core idea of these theories as a foundation for this study is centred on the funds component, which primarily represents remittances from Nigerians living abroad, sent to friends and family. This acts as an external factor that stimulates economic growth, and the satisfaction that the remitters feel from knowing they are contributing to this growth in some way.

Research Methodology

This study adopted an ex post facto research approach to empirically assess the influence of remittances from Nigeria's diaspora on Nigeria's economic growth. Secondary data were utilised for this research. These sources include the World Bank database and the annual report of the Central Bank of Nigeria (CBN) from 1987 to 2021.

Model specification

To examine the effects of remittances on economic growth in Nigeria, this study used the conventional ordinary least squares (OLS) regression technique as the estimation method within the autoregressive distributed lag (ARDL) model. This is illustrated in the functional and econometric equations. Therefore:

$$GDP = f(REM, EXCR).....1$$

In light of this, taking into consideration the models and the proxies that correspond to them, the econometric equation that results from the ordinary least squares (OLS) dynamics is as follows:

$$\log GDP = b_0 + b_1 \log REM + b_2 \log EXCR + et.....2$$

Where:

- GDP = Gross domestic product
- REM = Diaspora remittances
- EXCR = Exchange rate
- Regression constant = b_0
- Regression coefficient = $b_1 - b_5$
- Stochastic error term = et

Theoretically, it is expected that the proxies of remittances should positively impact economic growth in Nigeria ($b_1, b_2 > 0$) as an a priori expectation, ceteris paribus.

The Autoregressive Distributed Lag (ARDL) test was selected as the estimation method for this study. The study used the unconstrained vector model, which was successfully implemented employing the ARDL co-integration approach. The ARDL model for the estimated equations was developed as follows:

$$\Delta \log GDP_t = \alpha_0 + \sum_{k=1}^n a_1 \Delta \log REM_t + \sum_{k=1}^n a_4 \Delta \log EXCR_t + p_1 \Delta \log REM_{t-k} + p_4 \Delta \log EXCR_{t-k} + e..2$$

The ARDL approach can be employed when the variables are either purely I (0), I (1), or a mix of both. ARDL enables a more accurate identification of the features of small samples.

Results and Discussion

Results

Descriptive analysis

Table 1 displays both the results of the descriptive analysis and a summary of the information on the independent and dependent variables. The investigation found the following mean values: 219.65 for economic growth (GDP), 10.00 for remittances (REM), and 126.91 for the exchange rate (EXCR). The median values were 136.39 for economic growth, represented by GDP, 2.27 for remittances, represented by REM, and 125.83 for the exchange rate, represented by EXCR.

The standard deviation reflects how much the data diverges from its respective averages: 179.66 for GDP (economic growth), 9.92 for remittances (REM), and 109.76 for the exchange rate (EXCR). Evaluating normality involved analysing skewness and kurtosis. The E-view results displayed skewness values of 0.38 (GDP), 0.13 (REM), and 0.87 (EXCR), indicating a negatively skewed distribution with longer left tails, suggesting that lower values occurred more frequently than the sample mean.

Table 1: Result of descriptive statistics

	GDP	REM	EXCR
Mean	219.6529	10.00192	126.9118
Median	136.3900	2.273000	125.8331
Std. Dev.	179.6655	9.927743	109.7640
Skewness	0.380725	0.132732	0.870976
Kurtosis	1.489633	1.127003	3.103188
Jarque-Bera	4.172312	5.218775	4.440687
Probability	0.124163	0.073580	0.108572
Observations	35	35	35

Source: E-views 12.0 software

Kurtosis values were below the standard threshold of 3.0 for GDP (1.48) and REM (1.12), indicating a flatter distribution. Conversely, the exchange rate (EXCR) had a kurtosis value of 3.10, signifying a leptokurtic distribution with more extreme values than a normal distribution. The Jarque-Bera values for GDP, REM, and EXCR all had p-values greater than 0.05, implying that the null hypothesis of normality cannot be rejected. Therefore, the data set appears to follow a normal distribution.

Unit root test

Table 2 presents the results of the Augmented Dickey-Fuller test for unit root analysis. These findings are also included in the table mentioned earlier. As shown in Table 4, the test results indicate that none of the variables were stationary at level $I(0)$. However, after applying the first difference, GDP, REM, and EXCR—which were not stationary at level because their calculated ADF statistics were below the critical ADF values at the 5% significance level—became stationary. This is because their calculated ADF statistics fell below the critical ADF values.

Table 2

Augmented Dickey-Fuller Test					
Variable	Level	5% Tabulated	1st Difference	5% Tabulated	Comments
GDP	-0.2377	-2.9511	-3.8994	-2.9540	1(1)
REM	-0.6757	-2.9511	-5.0687	-2.9540	1(1)
EXCR	2.3868	-2.9511	-3.5685	-2.9540	1(1)

Source: E-views 12.0 software

ARDL cointegrating and long-run form

The result of the unit root test exercise offers evidence supporting the hypothesis by indicating the order of integration as I (1). The conclusion drawn from the ARDL cointegration test findings is that a relationship exists among the model's variables over the long term. In light of the results presented in Table 3, it is crucial to provide an estimate of the long-run coefficients.

Table 3: Long-run estimation

Levels Equation				
Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistic	Prob.
LREM	0.315649	0.295726	1.067369	0.3109
LEXCR	1.200408	0.444686	2.699450	0.0223
C	-11.68913	9.062702	-1.289806	0.2261

Source: E-views 12.0 statistical software

In the long term, it was concluded that a percentage increase in remittances (REM) would be statistically insignificant at the 5% level and, all other factors remaining constant, would result in a proportional decrease in Nigeria's economic growth (GDP) of 0.31%. These findings are based on the ARDL's long-term projections. Similar to the ARDL estimate, which was found to be statistically significant at the 5% level in the long run, an increase in the exchange rate (EXCR) is expected to lead to a corresponding decline in Nigeria's economic growth (GDP) of 1.20 percentage points, assuming all other conditions stay the same.

ARDL short-run dynamics test

The intercept value of -1.92 suggests that Nigeria's GDP would decrease by 1.92 per cent when all the independent variables are held constant (REM and EXCR). At the 5% level of statistical significance, this result is considered statistically significant. Additionally, the analysis shows that the ARDL model as a whole has a very high level of accuracy, as indicated by the R2 (R-squared) coefficient of 0.9989 (99.89 per cent). This means that about 99.89% of the variation in the dependent variable is explained by the independent factors. Furthermore, the adjusted R2 value is 0.9969, representing 99.69% of the total variation.

The current period of remittances (REM) had a non-significant positive effect on Nigeria's economic growth (GDP) in the short run. The previous lagged period had a significant positive effect, while the

two earlier lagged periods showed a significant negative effect. This suggests that, all other factors being equal, a change in remittances (REM) would soon influence Nigeria's GDP.

Table 4: ARDL short-run dynamic result

Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistic	Prob.*
LGDP(-1)	0.835404	0.081177	10.29115	0.0000
LREM	0.037330	0.034303	1.088267	0.3020
LREM(-1)	0.093780	0.026051	3.599813	0.0048
LREM(-2)	-0.079156	0.024138	-3.279282	0.0083
LEXCR	0.107876	0.074615	1.445771	0.1788
LEXCR(-1)	0.186059	0.069728	2.668361	0.0236
LEXCR(-2)	-0.096352	0.062545	-1.540513	0.1545
CointEq(-1)*	-0.164596	0.013239	-12.43238	0.0000
C	-1.923986	0.709948	-2.710037	0.0219
R ²	0.998990	Mean		5.089180
Adjusted R ²	0.996969	SD		0.999272

Source: E-views 12.0 statistical software

More specifically, it was found that the ARDL short-run estimates indicated that changes in the current period of the exchange rate (EXCR) had a nonsignificant positive effect on Nigeria's economic growth (GDP). Changes in the previous lagged period of the variable had a significant positive impact on GDP. In contrast, changes in the two preceding periods had an insignificant adverse effect on economic growth. This suggests that, all else being equal, a percentage increase or decrease in the exchange rate (EXCR) would result in a corresponding rise or fall in Nigeria's GDP in the short term. The ceteris paribus condition supports this. Finally, the value of the coefficient (CointEq (-1)) is -0.1645, indicating that the system successfully regained equilibrium at a rate of 16.45% per year.

Post-estimation tests

Post-estimation tests were conducted to assess the validity of the model and determine whether the regression results are suitable for policy advice. Consequently, tests for serial correlation, heteroskedasticity, and stability were carried out, and the findings are presented and analysed.

Test for serial correlation

As mentioned, the Breusch-Godfrey serial correlation test will be used to check for serial correlation. The decision rule is to reject the null hypothesis (i.e., there is no serial correlation) if the P-value of the observed R-squared is less than 0.05 (i.e., 5 per cent). Otherwise, we do not reject the null hypothesis.

Table 5: Serial Correlation Result

Breusch-Godfrey Serial Correlation LM Test			
Null hypothesis: No serial correlation at up to 2 lags			
F-statistics	3.275889	Prob. F (2, 8)	0.0913
Obs*R-squared	8.395741	Prob. Chi-Square (2)	0.0909

Source: E-views 12 statistical software

Table 5 indicates that the p-values for F-stat (3.275) and Obs*R-squared (8.395) are both above 0.05, which supports our assumption of no serial correlation in the ARDL model. Therefore, we accept the null hypothesis.

Test for Heteroscedasticity

The Breusch-Pagan-Godfrey heteroskedasticity test is used to determine whether the ARDL model's parameter estimations exhibit homoscedastic behaviour. This test did not indicate whether the estimates are homoskedastic or whether the model is heteroskedastic.

Table 6: Heteroscedasticity Test

Heteroskedasticity Test: Breusch-Pagan-Godfrey			
Null hypothesis: Homoskedasticity			
F-statistics	0.342052	Prob. F(10, 20)	0.9803
Obs*R-squared	12.59258	Prob. Chi-Square (20)	0.8942
Scaled explained SS	3.154628	Prob. Chi-Square (20)	1.0000

Source: E-views 12 statistical software

Table 6 summarises the findings from the Breusch-Pagan-Godfrey test for heteroskedasticity. We observed that the R2 value was 12.59, and the associated prob. Chi-square value was 89.42%. This indicates that the equation estimations were homoscedastic at a level greater than 5%. In other words, the ARDL model showed no signs of heteroscedasticity when tested at a 5% significance level.

Impulse response function (IRF)

The Cholesky one-standard-deviation innovation was used for over ten years to analyse the impulse response functions. Table 7 presents the results of the impulse response function, showing that the first year's gross domestic product responded positively to its shock. The positive response indicates this. The first year had a value of 0.1548, the second year 0.1433, the third year 0.1311, the fourth year 0.0957, the fifth year 0.0979, the sixth year 0.1150, the seventh year 0.1273, the eighth year 0.1273, the ninth year 0.1121, and the tenth year 0.0879.

In a similar vein, the findings presented in Table 12 showed that gross domestic product responded positively to shocks caused by remittances in the first year (0.0000), the second year (0.0505), the third year (0.0492), the fourth year (0.0304), the fifth year (0.0282), the sixth year (0.0318), the seventh year (0.0363), the eighth year (0.0368), the ninth year (0.0340), and the tenth year (0.0293). Similarly, the findings indicated that the gross domestic product reacted favorably to changes in the exchange rate during the first year (0.0000), the second year (0.0032), the third year (0.0332), the fourth year (0.0342), the fifth year (0.0522), the sixth year (0.0653), the seventh year (0.0710), the eighth year (0.0716), the ninth year (0.0671), and the tenth year (0.0671).

Table 7: Impulse response function (IRF)

Response of LGDP:			
Period	LGDP	LREM	LEXCR
1	0.154840	0.000000	0.000000
2	0.143317	0.050507	0.003258
3	0.131182	0.049217	0.033241
4	0.095750	0.030477	0.034243
5	0.097969	0.028297	0.052289

6	0.115075	0.031827	0.065366
7	0.127301	0.036346	0.071079
8	0.127304	0.036899	0.071612
9	0.112126	0.034038	0.067199
10	0.087953	0.029395	0.060875

Source: E-view 12.0 software

Discussion of findings

The results of the ARDL analysis indicate that remittances have a minimal impact on Nigeria's economic growth, both domestically and internationally, as noted by the researchers. Remittances refer to the funds that Nigerians abroad send home through the banking system. These remittances are crucial for helping the country meet its financial needs; however, when compared to the country's GDP, their influence is almost negligible. Therefore, remittances are unlikely to significantly contribute to increasing physical capital or productivity, which are essential for enhancing employment, improving living standards, and promoting overall economic development. It is also suggested that Nigeria's foreign currency policy might be a factor in the decline of remittances from its diaspora.

This conclusion aligns with the findings of Fagbola, Adebrite, and Oke (2020), which indicated that remittances have a somewhat positive impact on Nigeria's economic growth. Similarly, the research supports the work of Onyeisi, Odo, and Anoke (2018), who found a positive but non-significant correlation between the growth rate of international remittance inflows and domestic private sector credit in the short term. However, these findings contrast with those of Ugherughe and Okonkwo (2020), who demonstrated that the relationship between Nigeria's economy and remittance inflows from the diaspora is stable only in the long run.

Furthermore, the ARDL results indicate that the exchange rate has a significant negative impact on economic growth in the long run. In contrast, its effect is notably positive in the short term. This suggests that the exchange rate plays a crucial role in stimulating economic growth, as it has a direct impact on key economic factors, including domestic price levels, the profitability of traded goods and services, resource allocation, and investment decisions. This understanding explains why both monetary authorities and the private sector focus on maintaining stability in these economic parameters.

These findings align with the research by Okonkwo, Egbunike, and Udeh (2015) and further support the conclusions of Ugherughe and Okonkwo (2020), who discovered a direct and positive link between the exchange rate and economic growth. In general, the results suggest that over a long period, there is an equilibrium relationship between Nigeria's economy and remittance inflows from its diaspora.

Conclusion and Recommendations

The paper used total remittances and the currency exchange rate as independent variable proxies to empirically assess the impact of diaspora remittances on Nigeria's economic growth. According to the study's findings, it can be concluded that, in the long term, remittances from the diaspora have a negligible adverse effect on Nigeria's economic growth. In contrast, the volatile exchange rate has a significant negative impact. Although their overall benefits are minor, both expatriate remittances and a stable exchange rate were found to be advantageous for economic development in the short term. The research showed that the contribution of remittances varies depending on the lag considered, sometimes showing positive or negative effects.

The study recommends:

1. Further research to assess the impact of post-COVID-19 remittances from the diaspora on Nigeria's economic growth, particularly in light of the currency exchange rate's volatility.

2. Additionally, the government should boost its investment in infrastructure and improve access to essential services to attract more investors and increase their capital investments.
3. Moreover, the government must develop and implement a comprehensive monetary and fiscal recovery plan to address issues related to fluctuations in exchange rate movements within the economy.

References

- Adolphus, A. (2021). Enough of Nigeria's dependence on diaspora remittance: The Guardian, (Nigeria), Business a.m., Africa Business Radio series, 1-5.
- Adenike, A. (2021). The effect of migrant remittance on economic growth in Nigeria: An empirical study. National School of Political and Administrative Studies, Bucharest, Romania. Open Journal of Political Science. 11, 99-122
- Adewale, B. J., Ameji, N. E., & Solomon, U. P. (2021). Diaspora remittances and the growth of the Nigerian economy. Journal of the Institute of Social Sciences, 8(2). 170-185. <https://doi.org/10.30803/adusobed.975567>
- Ariam, B. & Lucas, W. (2018). The impact of remittances on the economic growth of developing countries: A literature review. Journal of International Business Management, Malardalen University, Vasteras, Sweden.
- Akin, O. (2020). Diaspora remittances and Nigeria's economic growth: The Guardian (Nigeria), Africa Business Radio series 1-7.
- Andualem, K. (2021). COVID-19: The impact of the global crisis on African remittances and countries' response to the extreme crisis: Cogent Economics & Finance Journal, Taylor and Francis. .9 (1).19,48,66,194.
- Asogwa, F. & Osondu, M. (2014). The impact of foreign direct investment on economic growth in Nigeria: IOSR Journal of Economic and Finance. 3, 37-45.
- David, R. T. (2015). African diaspora and remittances: Centre for Finance, Law, Policy, Boston University. www.bu.edu/bucflp
- Fagbola, O., Adegbite, E., & Oke, B. (2020). The effects of FDI and remittances on the economy in Nigeria: International Journal of Trade, Economics and Finance, 11(2).
- Giuliano, P., & Ruiz-Arranz, M. (2006). Remittances, financial development, and growth: Journal of the Institute for the Study of Labor, Bonn.
- Gelb, S., Kalantaryan, S., McMahon, S., & Perez-Fernandez, M. (2021). Diaspora Finance for Development: From Remittances to Investment. Journal of Joint Research Center of the European Union, Luxembourg.
- Godwin A. A. & Sergius N. U. (2021). Exchange rate and economic growth in Nigeria: Advance Journal of Management and Social Sciences, 5(05). Published by the International Institute of Advanced Scholars Development.
- Ibrahim, M. Y., Baajon, M. A. & Ezra, R. (2024). The Effect of Remittance on Economic Growth: Evidence of Nigeria Economy. Global Journal of Research in Business Management, 5(1). 5-15. DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.14750863
- Jiang, X., Oppong, S. & Vitenu-Sakey, P. (2019). The impact of personal remittances, FDI, and exports on economic growth: Evidence from West Africa. School of Finance and Economics, Jiangsu University, No. 301 Xuefu Road, Zhenjiang, Jiangsu Province, P.R., China. European Journal of Business and Management. 11 (23).

- Kalandi, C. & Charan, P. (2016). Does remittance drive economic growth in emerging economies: BRIC Evidence from FMOLS and Panel VECM? *Theoretical and Applied Economics Journal*, 26, (4) 57–74.
- Lynne, J. B. (2013). The effect of diaspora remittances on economic growth in Kenya: Master of Business Administration, Faculty of Arts and Social Sciences, Law, Business Management, University of Nairobi.
- Mgbarine, A. C., Olulu, R. M., & Lawrence, O. (2022). Diaspora remittances and economic growth nexus in Nigeria. *Academic Journal of Current Research*, 9(10). 45 – 53. [file:///C:/Users/USER/Downloads/CIRD-AJCR-22-0932+final%20\(2\).pdf](file:///C:/Users/USER/Downloads/CIRD-AJCR-22-0932+final%20(2).pdf)
- Muriel, A. A. (2015). Impact of remittances on economic growth: Evidence from selected West African countries: (Cameroon, Cape Verde, Nigeria, and Senegal). *Journal of African Human Mobility Review*, 1(2).
- Okonkwo, R., Egbunike, F. & Udeh, F. (2015). Foreign direct investment and economic growth in Nigeria: *Developing Country Studies*, 5(9).
- Onah, G. I. (2010). The effects of remittances on poverty and human capital formation in Nigeria: <http://w.w.w.un.edu.ng/publications/files>
- Oluyemi, F., Azuh, D. & Agayi, L. (2015). The impact of remittances on Nigeria's economic growth: A study of Nigeria's diaspora in Ghana. *Journal of South African Business Research*.
- Onyeisi, O., Odo, I. & Anoke, I. (2018). Remittance inflow and domestic credit to the private sector: The Nigerian experience. *IOSR Journal of Business and Management*, 20, 28-38.
- Orekoya, S., and Tijan, I. (2023). Do diaspora remittances contribute to human capital development in Nigeria? *African Journal for the Psychological Study of Social Studies*, 26(3). 27-39
- Ozigbu, J. C. (2018). Social-Economic implications of migrants' dollars in Nigeria: *IOSR Journal of Economics and Finance*, 9, 51-59.
- Stark, O. (1995). In *Altruism and Beyond: An Economic Analysis of transfers and exchange within families and groups*: Journal of Oscar Morgenstern Memorial Lectures, Cambridge.
- Samuel, O. (2021). Diaspora remittances into Nigeria fall by 24% in Q1 2021: *Journal of Nairametrics.com*.
- Suman, B., Sridharan, P., Rabindra, K. & Chandrika, P. (2021). Causal Linkage between Remittances and Financial Development: Evidence from BRICS (Brazil, Russia, India, China, and South Africa). *Journal of East-West Business*.
- Ugherughe, J., & Okonkwo, J. (2020). Diaspora Remittance and Nigeria's Economy: An Empirical Analysis (1977-2017). *Journal of Management Science Sahel Analyst*, 2
- Zainab, A. (2021). Bolster economy with diaspora remittances: *Punch Editorial Board* pp. 1-4